

Used quantities

Reduced Compton wavelength, aka Compton radius	$r_c = \lambda_c/2\pi = \hbar/(mc)$
Angular Compton frequency	$\omega_c = c/r_c = mc^2/\hbar$
Angular de Broglie frequency	$\omega_b = v/r_c = mvc/\hbar$
Distance r quantified in Compton radius multiples	$N = r/r_c$
Inverse of Compton radius quantified in Planck length multiples	$A_B = 1/(r_c/l_l)$
Acoustic impedance of space	$Z_s = c^3/(2G l_l^2)$
Total special relativistic energy	$E_\gamma = \hbar\sqrt{\omega_c^2 + \gamma^2 \omega_b^2}$
Lorentz factor of special relativity	$\gamma = \sqrt{1 - v^2/c^2}$
Classical escape speed from a mass m	$s = \sqrt{2Gm/r}$
Inverse of distance r quantified in Planck length multiples	$l_l/r = 1/(r/l_l)$

Comparison of classical forces

Force	Classical	Planck form	Macken notation	Wave equation form
Gravitational	$G \frac{m_1 m_2}{r^2}$	$\frac{1}{4} F_l \frac{s_1^2 s_2^2}{c^2 c^2}$	$F_l \frac{A_{B1}^2}{N_1} \frac{A_{B2}^2}{N_2}$	$l_l^2 \left(\frac{\omega_{c1} \omega_{c2}}{\omega_l} \right)^2 Z_s \left[2 \frac{r_{c1}}{r/l_l} \frac{r_{c2}}{r/l_l} \right] \frac{1}{c}$
Electrostatic (sp. case)	$\frac{1}{4\pi\epsilon_0} \frac{e^2}{r^2}$	$\alpha F_l \frac{l_l^2}{r^2}$	$\alpha F_l \frac{A_{B1}}{N_1} \frac{A_{B2}}{N_2}$	$\alpha l_l^2 (\omega_{c1} \omega_{c2}) Z_s \left[2 \frac{r_{c1}}{r/l_l} \frac{r_{c2}}{r/l_l} \right] \frac{1}{c}$
Magnetic (sp. case)	$\frac{\mu_0}{4\pi} \frac{e^2 v_1 v_2}{r^2}$	$\alpha F_l \frac{l_l^2}{r^2} \frac{v_1 v_2}{c^2}$	$\alpha F_l \frac{A_{B1}}{N_1} \frac{A_{B2}}{N_2} \frac{v_1 v_2}{c^2}$	$\alpha l_l^2 (\omega_{b1} \omega_{b2}) Z_s \left[2 \frac{r_{c1}}{r/l_l} \frac{r_{c2}}{r/l_l} \right] \frac{1}{c}$

Natural constants

Light speed	$c = 2.9979 \times 10^8$ m/s
Planck constant	$h = 2\pi\hbar = 6.6261 \times 10^8$ J/Hz
Gravitational constant	$G = 6.6743 \times 10^{-11}$ m ³ /(s ² kg)
Electric field constant	$\epsilon_0 = 8.8542 \times 10^{-12}$ F/m
Magnetic field constant	$\mu_0 = 1.2567 \times 10^{-6}$ mT/A
Fundamental charge	$e = 1.6022 \times 10^{-19}$ C
Sommerfeld constant	$\alpha = e^2/(2ch\epsilon_0) \cong 1/137$
Magnetic flux quantum	$\phi_e = h/2e$
Planck length	$l_l = \sqrt{\hbar/c} \times \sqrt{G/c^2} = \sqrt{\hbar G/c^3} = 1.6162 \times 10^{-35}$ m
Planck mass	$m_l = \sqrt{\hbar/c} \times \sqrt{c^2/G} = \sqrt{\hbar c/G} = 21.765$ μ g
Planck time	$t_l = \sqrt{\hbar/c} \times \sqrt{G/c^2} \times \sqrt{1/c^2} = \sqrt{\hbar G/c^5} = l_l/c = 5.3912 \times 10^{-44}$ s
Planck charge	$\pm q_l = \pm e/\sqrt{\alpha} = \pm 1.876 \times 10^{-18}$ C
Planck force	$F_l = c^4/G = 1.21 \times 10^{44}$ N

Relation between gravity, electrostatic force and Planck force

From the above force comparison table it can be deduced that there is the following relationship between the gravitational attraction $F_{gc} = Gm_1m_2/r^2$ and the electrostatic attraction $F_{ec} = e^2/(4\pi\epsilon_0r^2)$ for two charged spin $\frac{1}{2}$ particles.

$$\left[\frac{1}{\alpha} \frac{F_{ec}}{F_l} \right]^2 N_1 N_2 = \frac{F_{gc}}{F_l}$$

This square relationship is also reflected in the powers of the respective A_β variables in the "Macken notation" column of the above force comparison table. The square relationship is even more obvious for identical particles, i.e. when $N_1 N_2 = N^2$.

Being able to relate F_{ge} to F_{gc} without the gravitational constant G , once both forces are normalized relative to the Planck force F_l , suggests that the electrostatic force and the gravitational force are not fully independent entities.

It's also possible to write the previous relation as a ratio of gravity and electrostatic force to electrostatic force and the Planck force

$$\frac{F_{gc}/(N_1 N_2)}{F_{ec}/\alpha^2} = \frac{F_{ec}}{F_l}$$

or alternatively as a kind of geometric mean

$$\frac{\sqrt{F_l F_{gc}}}{\sqrt{N_1 N_2}} = \frac{F_{ec}}{\alpha}$$

For cases of identical particles at a distance r where $N_1 = N_2 = 1$ the previous relation becomes quite intriguing as it suggests a deeper connection between the involved forces.

Please also note that the Planck force F_l is closely linked to the forces between black holes and that it presumably represents the upper force limit in our universe.